

1 **T cells of all major subsets express MBD2 and CHD4.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 Citations

7 1. Ng, H.H., Zhang, Y., Hendrich, B., Johnson, C.A., Turner, B.M., Erdjument-Bromage, H., Tempst,
8 P., Reinberg, D. and Bird, A., 1999. MBD2 is a transcriptional repressor belonging to the MeCP1 histone
9 deacetylase complex. *Nature genetics*, 23(1), pp.58-61.

10 2. Xia, L., Huang, W., Bellani, M., Seidman, M.M., Wu, K., Fan, D., Nie, Y., Cai, Y., Zhang, Y.W., Yu,
11 L.R. and Li, H., 2017. CHD4 has oncogenic functions in initiating and maintaining epigenetic suppression
12 of multiple tumor suppressor genes. *Cancer cell*, 31(5), pp.653-668.